

Enhancing Multimodal Reasoning with Data Alignment and Fusion

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ENHANCING MULTIMODAL REASONING WITH DATA ALIGNMENT AND FUSION

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School of Innovation, Design and Engineering

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Abstract

Multimodal machine learning (MML) significantly transformed the development of artificial intelligence (AI) systems. Instead of working with single source data, it integrated and analysed information from multiple modalities, such as images, audio, text, sensors, and more. The volume of labelled and unlabelled multimodal data increased rapidly, but effectively using them, especially managing unlabelled multimodal data, poses significant challenges. Existing approaches usually depend on supervised learning and struggle to handle the heterogeneity and complexity of such data. These limitations interrupted the creation of good, scalable, and generalised MML systems that can use the full potential of this diverse data.

This thesis addressed this demanding challenge by using multimodal reasoning. To this end, a scheme was introduced for advancing multimodal reasoning by effectively using unlabelled multimodal data. The scheme was designed on inferential steps to use the latent knowledge and patterns hidden within these vast unlabelled datasets. These inferential steps mitigated the limitation of supervised methods, which solely depend on a vast amount of labelled data, which is difficult to get in real-world scenarios. The selection of unique inferential steps was based on their specific strengths in addressing challenges in unlabelled multimodal data. The scheme starts with using the unsupervised approach to extract features, which are then used as input for a clustering approach to group similar data points based on their hidden characteristics. This clustering approach sets the stage for applying a semi-supervised approach to intelligently assign labels to the clustered data, efficiently converting unlabelled

data into a useful and structured resource.

The validity of the proposed approach is carefully evaluated on unlabelled vehicular datasets collected in real time. The proposed approach showed the ability to achieve more than 90% accuracy by using a newly labelled dataset. Furthermore, this research dove into the exciting field of transfer learning. It explored its potential to enhance multimodal reasoning by using knowledge gained from one dataset to improve performance on another. A novel model based on the transformer architecture is specifically designed to handle continuous features available in multimodal data. The result of the model was satisfactory and showed that the performance of the state-of-the-art was better than traditional machine learning (ML) algorithms.

This thesis research made significant and multifaceted contributions to the research on MML. It provided an extensive analysis of MML and its challenges, including existing approaches on alignment and fusion, by focusing on their limitations and identifying gaps in current research. Moreover, it introduced an effective approach for labelling unlabelled datasets through a series of carefully designed inferential steps, which shows a path for more efficient and scalable multimodal learning. Finally, it presented the outstanding potential of transfer learning, particularly with a transformer-based model, to advance multimodal reasoning. The insights, techniques, and results presented in this thesis held the potential to reveal a new edge in MML research and provide an opportunity to develop more useful, scalable, and data-efficient models to tackle real-world challenges across a wide range of applications.

Sammanfattning

Multimodal maskininlärning (MML) förändrade avsevärt utvecklingen av artificiell intelligens (AI). I stället för att arbeta med data från en enda källa, integrerade och analyserade MML information från flera modaliteter, såsom bilder, ljud, text, sensorer och mer. Mängden märkta och omärkta multimodala data ökade snabbt, men att effektivt använda dem, särskilt hantering av omärkta multimodala data, innebär betydande utmaningar. Befintliga tillvägagångssätt är vanligtvis beroende av övervakat lärande som kämpar med att hantera heterogeniteten och komplexiteten hos sådan data. Dessa begränsningar avbröt skapandet av bra, skalbara och generaliserade MML system som kan använda den fulla potentialen av denna mångsidiga data.

Denna avhandling tog upp denna krävande utmaning genom att använda multimodala resonemang. För detta ändamål infördes ett system för att främja multimodala resonemang genom att effektivt använda omärkt multimodala data. Schemat utformades genom slutledning för att använda den latent kunskapen och mönstren gömda i dessa enorma omärkta datamängder. Dessa slutsatser mildrade begränsningen av övervakade metoder, som enbart beror på en stor mängd märkt data, vilket är svårt att få tag på i verkliga scenarier. Valet av unika slutledningssteg baserades på deras specifika styrkor när det gäller att hantera utmaningar i omärkta multimodala data. Schemat börjar med att använda det oövervakade tillvägagångssättet för att extrahera funktioner, som sedan används som indata för en klustringsmetod för att gruppera liknande datapunkter baserat på deras dolda egenskaper. Denna klustringsmetod sätter scenen för att tillämpa en semi-övervakad metod för att intelligent tilldela etiketter

till grupperade data, vilket effektivt konverterar omärkta data till en användbar och strukturerad resurs.

Giltigheten av den föreslagna metoden utvärderas noggrant på omärkta for-
donsdatauppsättningar som samlas in i realtid. Det föreslagna tillvägagångssät-
tet visade förmågan att uppnå mer än 90% noggrannhet genom att använda nyli-
gen sorterade data. Dessutom fördjupade denna forskning in i det spännande
området transfer learning. Den undersökte dess potential att förbättra multi-
modala resonemang genom att använda kunskap från en datauppsättning för att
förbättra prestanda på en annan. En ny modell baserad på transformatorarkitek-
turen är speciellt utformad för att hantera kontinuerliga funktioner som är till-
gängliga i multimodala data. Resultatet av modellen var tillfredsställande och
visade att prestandan för toppmodernerna var bättre än traditionella maskininlärn-
ing (ML) algoritmer.

Denna avhandlingsforskning gav betydande och mångfacetterade bidrag
till forskningen om MML. Den gav en omfattande analys av MML och dess
utmaningar, inklusive befintliga metoder för anpassning och fusion, genom
att fokusera på deras begränsningar och identifiera luckor i aktuell forskn-
ing. Dessutom introducerade den ett effektivt tillvägagångssätt för att märka
omärkta datamängder genom en serie noggrant utformade slutledningssteg, som
visar en väg för mer effektiv och skalbar multimodal inläring. Slutligen pre-
senterade den enastående potentialen hos överföringslärande, särskilt med en
transformatorbaserad modell, för att främja multimodala resonemang. De in-
sikter, tekniker och resultat som presenteras i denna avhandling innehöll poten-
tialen att avslöja ett nytt försprång inom MML forskning och ge en möjlighet
att utveckla mer användbara, skalbara och dataeffektiva modeller för att tackla
verkliga utmaningar inom ett brett spektrum av applikationer.

To Buddha and My Parents

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Arnab Barua
Västerås, November, 2024

¹<https://www.fitdrive.eu/>

List of Publications

Papers included in this thesis²

Paper A: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shahina Begum. *A Systematic Literature Review on Multimodal Machine Learning: Applications, Challenges, Gaps and Future Directions*. Journal of IEEE Access (IEEE Access), Volume 11, 2023.

Paper B: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shahina Begum. *Multi-scale Data Fusion and Machine Learning for Vehicle Manoeuvre Classification*. In the 13th International Conference on System Engineering and Technology (ICSET), 2023.

Paper C: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shaibal Barua, Shahina Begum, Andrea Giorgi. *Second-Order Learning with Grounding Alignment: A Multimodal Reasoning Approach to Handle Unlabelled Data*. In the 16th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence - Volume 2: ICAART, 2024.

Paper D: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shahina Begum. *Advanced Hybrid Reasoning and Transfer Learning on Multimodal Data with Transformers* [Under review]. Springer Nature Computer Science.

²The included papers have been reformatted to comply with the thesis layout.

Publications not included in this thesis

Paper E: Andrea Giorgi, Vincenzo Ronca, Alessia Vozzi, Pietro Aricò, Gianluca Borghini, Rossella Capotorto, Luca Tamborra, Ilaria Simonetti, Simone Sportiello, Marco Petrelli, Carlo Polidori, Rodrigo Varga, Marteyn Van Gasteren, Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Fabio Babiloni, Gianluca Di Flumeri. “*Neurophysiological mental fatigue assessment for developing user-centered Artificial Intelligence as a solution for autonomous driving.*” Journal of Frontiers in Neurorobotics, 2023.

Paper F: Adil Mustafa, Daniyal Haider, Arnab Barua, Melikhan Tanyeri, Ahmet Erten, Ozlem Yalcin. “*Machine learning based microfluidic sensing device for viscosity measurements.*” Journal of The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2023.

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I

Thesis

Chapter 1

Introduction

The human mind has an incredible capability to process vast amounts of information, find meanings from very complex patterns, and make decisions even when faced with incomplete data. This remarkable ability comes from the human's capacity for reasoning. Reasoning is the process of using information to build conclusions and provide solutions to problems. This cognitive process helps humans to draw logical conclusions based on information available to them [1]. In the age of artificial intelligence (AI), reasoning serves a similar function by empowering intelligent machines to replicate certain aspects of human intelligence [2]. This encompasses the use of algorithms and data to work together to draw logical inferences, identify connections between different pieces of information, and create new knowledge. This reasoning ability is important for enhancing decision-making in machine learning (ML). It allows models to move beyond simple pattern recognition and develop a deeper understanding of the underlying relationships within the data. For instance, in the field of medical diagnosis, using reasoning in ML not only suggests possible diagnoses but also provides clues behind them.

Based on this idea of reasoning, multimodal reasoning expands this competence to include knowledge from multiple modalities [3]. These modalities can encompass various types of data, such as text, images, audio, and sensor data.

In the context of multimodal machine learning (MML), multimodal reasoning refers to the creation of models that can combine information and adequately process these diverse modalities to achieve more extensive and robust conclusions [3, 4]. This ability to reason across different modalities is essential in MML because it allows models to emulate the human capacity to process information from multiple modalities. It leads to a more comprehensive and robust understanding of the task at hand. For example, a multimodal reasoning system can produce a more precise recipe by analysing both the textual description and visual presentation of a dish.

Despite its potential, the implementation of multimodal reasoning poses significant challenges. The nature of multimodal data itself is primarily responsible for these challenges [5]. One challenge is related to the integration and interpretation of heterogeneous data. Multimodal data is characterised by its heterogeneity, encompassing different modalities with distinct qualities, structures, and representations that have unique statistical properties [3]. The diversity in information, noise, and task relevance makes managing this heterogeneity crucial to effective multimodal reasoning [4]. Another significant challenge in multimodal reasoning is the interconnection between these diverse modalities. Despite their heterogeneity, these modalities often contain related and complementary information. Accurately capturing these interconnections requires sophisticated methodologies, especially in complex tasks [6]. Furthermore, multimodal data is often unlabelled, which poses a significant challenge, especially for supervised learning algorithms that depend on labelled examples to identify patterns and make precise predictions [7]. For example, training a model to identify emotions from videos necessitates labelled data linking certain facial expressions, vocal tones, and body language to the corresponding emotions. The model finds it hard to learn these complex connections without such labels, making accurate multimodal reasoning hard to accomplish.

The challenges associated with multimodal data require the development of robust methods for implementing multimodal reasoning. Two crucial approaches addressing these challenges, particularly with unlabelled data, are multimodal alignment and multimodal fusion. Alignment helps establish cross-

modal connections and interactions of data across different modalities, making sure that the information is accurately synchronised [4, 8]. This systematically reduces the complexity arising from heterogeneity. For example, the process of aligning the visual characteristics of a bird in an image with the textual description in a caption. This alignment process is beneficial in addressing the heterogeneity of multimodal data by creating associations between various depictions of the same fundamental idea. On the other hand, multimodal fusion is the process of integrating information from multiple modalities with the aim of predicting an outcome [8, 9]. For instance, fusing facial expressions with textual sentiment analysis brings a more precise evaluation of an individual's emotional state. By merging each modality and capitalising on their alignment, multimodal fusion creates a more robust and incorporated representation of information. Multimodal alignment and fusion play a crucial role in successful multimodal reasoning as they ensure that data is processed in a connected and holistic manner rather than in isolation. Aligning and fusing data from various sources is a complex task that enables AI systems to effectively process and interpret multimodal data, resulting in more accurate and comprehensive reasoning.

In summary, this thesis explores the challenging area of multimodal reasoning, specifically focusing on effectively using unlabelled data. It demonstrates using unlabelled vehicular data and labelled neurophysiological data. ML methods often face difficulties when dealing with unlabelled datasets due to their reliance on true data labels. This research addresses this limitation by proposing solutions for handling unlabelled multimodal data through multimodal reasoning. The research explores various approaches, particularly emphasising multimodal alignment and fusion. In this context, alignment involves techniques for establishing correspondences and relationships between elements of vehicular and neurophysiological data. At the same time, fusion focuses on integrating information from these aligned modalities to create a unified and comprehensive representation. Traditional ML algorithms and state-of-the-art neural network-based methods are employed to unlock the potential of unlabelled vehicular data. By addressing the inherent challenges in this type

of data, this thesis aims to advance the field of multimodal reasoning and unleash its immense potential for solving intricate problems.

1.1 Research Goal and Objectives

With the growing amount of unlabelled data in different fields and the shortcomings of current multimodal reasoning methods in effectively using this data, this study investigates new approaches to address this issue. This progress has the potential to reveal valuable insights and abilities in a wide range of uses, from medical diagnosis to content understanding. The main goal of this thesis is:

To advance the field of multimodal reasoning by developing and analysing methods capable of effectively leveraging unlabelled data.

In this research, the following objectives are established to achieve the goal:

- Investigate the advancement of multimodal reasoning and its challenges in various application domains.
- Analyse and implement effective methods for multimodal alignment and fusion.
- Examine the advantages and drawbacks of various algorithmic methods for processing unlabelled multimodal data.
- Identify potential limitations of the proposed approaches and suggestions for future research.

1.2 Problem Formulation

MML has emerged as a strong example of creating intelligent systems capable of understanding and interacting like humans. Traditional ML approaches usually focus on a single modality, such as text or images. On the other hand,

multimodal learning tries to integrate and reason over information from multiple modalities, which has led to great advancements in various fields, such as healthcare, robotics, and human-computer interaction. However, properly processing and analysing multimodal data presents unique challenges. These challenges come from the heterogeneity characteristics of multimodal data, where each modality contains different kinds of statistical properties and representations. For example, merging text and visuals requires aligning the meaning in words with visual concepts in images. Moreover, multimodal data often contains noise, incompleteness and misalignment. Noise usually comes from the drawbacks of sensors in data collection, while incompleteness happens when data from one or more modalities is missing during collection. Misalignment means the data points of modalities are not temporally aligned even though they are related. These issues make it challenging to extract meaningful information from multimodal data using traditional single-modality approaches. To address these challenges, often techniques like alignment and fusion are applied, where alignment focuses on identifying relationships between elements in modalities to link semantic gaps and handle misalignment, and fusion tries to combine different modalities into a unified representation to tackle noise and incompleteness. Considerable progress has been made in developing alignment and fusion techniques to address these challenges [4, 10]. However, researchers still struggle with model design complexity and difficulties in evaluating multimodal data, especially when one of the modalities is missing [11]. Besides this, models used in MML face difficulties in maintaining performance when faced with new multimodal datasets or variations in data distributions, emphasising the need for more adaptable and resilient approaches. This research, therefore, aims to assess the effectiveness of existing alignment and fusion methods in MML and investigate new models for improvement.

Using multiple modalities, such as text, images, and sensor readings, has great potential in various fields. For example, in healthcare, combining patient's medical images with previous records could help predict diseases earlier. However, effectively handling and extracting knowledge from multimodal data becomes much more challenging when there is a lack of sufficient labelled

data. Current ML models heavily rely on labelled datasets. These models fail to identify hidden connections and patterns within diverse sources, especially when the data is unlabelled. Obtaining accurate, consistent, and complete labels for multimodal data is usually expensive and requires expert annotation for each data type and their relationships. It is also time-consuming as the process often requires manual verification and alignment. In some cases, such as analysing real-time video feeds for proper social interactions, creating extensive labels might be practically difficult due to the huge volume and complexity of the data. Therefore, it is crucial to explore approaches that can reveal the full potential of unlabelled, heterogeneous multimodal data, allowing for the extraction of meaningful insights, and advancing the understanding of complex phenomena, even in the absence of extensive labelled data.

The concept of multimodal learning offers great potential for advancing AI by combining and analysing data from various sources. This integration commonly relies on alignment and fusion to help machines establish meaningful connections and consolidate information from different modalities. However, as multimodal models become more complex and handle larger datasets to tackle more difficult tasks, getting both effective and efficient reasoning poses significant challenges. Recent approaches often struggle to achieve this balance when aligning and fusing heterogeneous data in an efficient, scalable, and adaptable manner. At the same time, dealing with a large amount of unlabelled multimodal data became more challenging, requiring sophisticated approaches to use the valuable information contained in this unlabelled data effectively. Therefore, it is essential to explore advanced methods to enhance the efficiency of multimodal reasoning across various aspects, including computational complexity, data utilisation, model robustness, and adaptability.

1.3 Research Questions

To facilitate the validation of the research with concrete outcomes, the research questions (RQs) are outlined below.

- **RQ 1:** *How effective are existing data fusion and alignment methods and how to improve them in the context of MML?*

A broad understanding of alignment and fusion techniques is essential for advancing MML. This research question (RQ) has been developed to investigate existing approaches and assess their strengths and limitations across various tasks and datasets. The ultimate goal is to lay the groundwork for the development of more robust, accurate, and efficient methods for aligning and fusing multimodal data, leading to the creation of more effective multimodal models.

- **RQ 2:** *How can multimodal heterogeneous data be effectively used in the absence of labels?*

Unlabelled multimodal data offers great potential but also comes with challenges. This RQ aims to explore how to efficiently handle diverse and heterogeneous multimodal data when accurate labels are not provided. The research investigates various approaches for interpreting and utilising such data, which is essential in unsupervised and semi-supervised learning scenarios. The aim is to unlock the potential of large, untapped multimodal datasets, even in the absence of labels.

- **RQ 3:** *How advanced ML techniques can enhance the efficiency of multimodal reasoning?*

The strength of multimodal reasoning stays in its capability to combine information from different sources, resulting in more reliable and insightful results. However, getting high accuracy and coherency in multimodal reasoning remains a significant challenge. This RQ investigates how advanced ML methods can be used to enhance the effectiveness of multimodal reasoning, leading to more accurate and reliable conclusions drawn from complex and diverse data sources. Through the development and evaluation of new methods, this RQ seeks to unleash the full potential of multimodal reasoning for various applications.

This thesis aims to answer the above RQs via a collection of scientific pub-

RQs	Paper A	Paper B	Paper C	Paper D
RQ1	✓	✓		
RQ2			✓	✓
RQ3			✓	✓

Table 1.1: Mapping of included papers to defined research questions.

lications. The included papers and their associated RQs are presented in Table 1.1.

1.4 Research Contributions

The RQs in section 1.3 are addressed through multiple research contributions published across various venues. These contributions include the following:

- **RC 1:** *Investigation of existing approaches for multimodal alignment and fusion.*

Numerous publications are available on different approaches to alignment and fusion in MML. Systematic exploration of scientific articles is necessary to understand the insights of multimodal alignment and fusion. This research contribution (RC) addresses this necessity by conducting an analysis of various existing methods. RC1 has been disseminated in two of the included papers of this thesis. *Paper A* is about a systematic literature review on MML and its challenges. Several available methods of alignment and fusion are investigated, along with highlighted challenges and future research directions. *Paper B* presents a fusion technique using a statistical approach instead of traditional approaches and its potential to enhance fusion.

- **RC 2:** *Approach for effectively labelling unlabelled multimodal data.*

The lack of labelled data in multimodal learning makes it difficult to train models effectively. This contribution addresses this issue by introducing

RCs	Paper A	Paper B	Paper C	Paper D
RC1	✓	✓		
RC2			✓	
RC3			✓	✓

Table 1.2: Mapping of included papers to research contributions

an innovative approach for accurate and effective labelling of multimodal data. In *Paper C*, the RC2 is disseminated, which involves aligning unlabelled and labelled datasets, selecting a subset of data based on similarity from the aligned dataset, applying a semi-supervised approach to propagate labels to the remaining unlabelled data, and validating the efficiency of this approach using a probability-related method.

- **RC 3:** *Enhancing multimodal reasoning through inferential techniques.*

In MML, reasoning is crucial, and it requires models capable of learning from different sources. It involves several inferential steps, such as feature extraction, cross-modal analysis, and inference-making. However, relying solely on labelled datasets creates a significant barrier. To address this, the focus of this contribution is to enhance multimodal reasoning by using inferential techniques for data labelling and decision-making. The RC3 is disseminated in *Papers C* and *D*, respectively. *Paper C* presents an inferential framework for labelling unlabelled multimodal data, involving steps like feature extraction, clustering, alignment, semi-supervised learning, and Bayesian verification. *Paper D* uses the inferential framework from *Paper C* and looks into transfer learning (TL) to improve multimodal reasoning.

In this study, the above contributions are depicted using unlabelled vehicular data and labelled neurophysiological data to detect drivers' mental fatigue while driving, which can contribute to safety systems for improving road safety. Table 1.2 presents the papers are included in the thesis and their target RCs.

1.5 Thesis Outline

- **Part I - Thesis** The remainder of this thesis is organised as follows: Chapter 2 contains the background knowledge and previous works done. Chapter 3 includes the research methodology and used methods. Description of the developed approach and results are represented in Chapter 4. Summary of the included papers presented in Chapter 5. Finally, Chapter 6 presents a discussion on approach, RQs, limitations, conclusion and future works.
- **Part II - Included Papers** This part includes four papers that have been reformatted to comply with this thesis layout from their original versions as published in or submitted to the respective journals or conferences.

Chapter 2

Background & Related Work

This chapter provides an overview of the background and related work in research areas that form the foundation of this thesis.

2.1 Multimodal Machine Learning

2.1.1 What is Modality?

In general, a modality means the way something is experienced or happens [8, 12]. From the human perspective, modality encompasses sensory experiences such as vision, sound, and touch [8]. From the ML perspective, modality can encompass different types of data that machines process, such as text, images, and audio. The term "modalities" is the plural form, which denotes the diversity and combination of various types of data, such as speech and audio recorded from a microphone, as well as images and videos captured through cameras. Modalities can be raw or abstract [4]. Raw modalities indicate that data comes directly from sensors, such as images from a camera or audio from a microphone. On the other hand, abstract modality involves extracting information from raw data, such as identifying objects from images or extracting language from audio.

2.1.2 What is Multimodal?

A research problem or dataset is considered multimodal when it involves multiple modalities [8]. It refers to a computational study that examines diverse and interconnected modalities, which can be understood through three foundational principles [4]. The first principle entails the heterogeneity of modalities, as they contain different types of information with distinct qualities, structures, and representations. For example, textual information is represented in characters, whereas image information is represented in pixels, each with its unique distribution. Modalities often contain complementary information, which allows them to establish connections between each other, forming the basis of the second principle. In an image captioning task, models identify connections between elements of the image (such as objects and colours) and the corresponding words in the text. The third principle involves interaction, where elements of modalities are combined to create new information. Using the example of image captioning, integrating elements of the image and text generates a textual caption from the visual modality.

2.1.3 Concept of Multimodal Machine Learning

MML is a rapidly growing multi-disciplinary research field in AI which aims to design systems capable of learning and making decisions through multiple modalities, such as language, sound, images, and physiological data [8, 13, 14]. In MML the predicted output \hat{y} can be expressed as,

$$\hat{y} = \bigcup_{i=1}^M f_i(m_i) \quad (2.1)$$

In Equation 2.1, M means the set of all modalities, with each modality identified as m_i , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$ denotes the i -th modality. The function $f_i(m_i)$ refers to a modality-specific function that processes input from modality m_i , such as extracting features or making initial predictions that are relevant to that modality. The integration of the outputs from all modality-specific func-

tions $f_i(m_i)$ is denoted by \cup . This notation highlights that the final output \hat{y} is achieved by combining information from each modality, taking advantage of their unique strengths. The combining process may involve techniques like alignment, merging, or other methods to combine the outputs of the different modalities into a unified prediction. This formulation captures the essence of MML, which enhances learning performance by integrating multiple data sources and achieving better results than relying on any single modality.

The idea of MML is depicted in Figure 2.1, where modalities go through different types of ML models, like supervised and unsupervised types, to make predictions. The core principles of developing effective MML depend on understanding the heterogeneity and interconnections between modalities [4]. The team¹ of researchers led by Associate Professor Louis-Philippe Morency² from Carnegie Mellon University provided a taxonomy of the technical challenges of MML in an article [8]. In a later update, they proposed six core technical challenges: representation, alignment, reasoning, generation, transference, and quantification, by considering the heterogeneity, connection, and interconnection principles of modality [4].

2.1.4 Related Work

There has been active research in developing methodologies to solve problems related to MML. Professor Louis-Philippe Morency and his team published an article [8] that classified the challenges of performing MML, which brought more focus to this area of research. Later, they updated and presented the core technical challenges of MML in another article [4]. At this time, no additional papers exist that discuss the foundation of MML. Several surveys are now available discussing the potential use of MML in different domains. For instance, authors in articles [15, 16, 17] summarised studies of MML in the healthcare domain and highlighted topics for future research. Additionally, authors of articles [13, 18, 19] conducted surveys in the computer vision domain, exploring

¹<http://multicomp.cs.cmu.edu/multimodal-machine-learning/>

²<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~morency/>

Figure 2.1: Conceptual figure of multimodal machine learning.

various concepts of MML. Moreover, in articles [20] and [21], authors surveyed the use of MML in communication and autonomous driving research. In addition to domain, numerous surveys have explored how MML (MML) can address issues related to different modalities. For example, [22] conducted a survey on meme classification, [23] focused on sentimental analysis, [24] covered visual and language analysis, [25] addressed content understanding, [26] examined neuroimage analysis, and [27] investigated multimodal label distribution. In the article [28], 374 articles are identified that address problems using methods related to MML. This proposed research aims to investigate different approaches to overcome the technical challenges associated with MML, with the goal of uncovering new insights in this field.

2.2 Multimodal Reasoning

2.2.1 What is Reasoning?

Understanding reasoning involves the process of drawing conclusions or judgments from a set of premises, which can involve one or several inferential steps

[29, 30, 31]. From a human perspective, reasoning encompasses cognitive processes such as identifying patterns, establishing relationships, and applying knowledge to make decisions [1]. According to article [32], reasoning can take the forms of formal and informal reasoning. In formal reasoning, the conclusion will be true as long as the premises are true; however, informal reasoning doesn't guarantee a true conclusion. Reasoning can also be categorised based on the direction of inference, such as deductive, inductive, abductive, and analogical [30]. Deductive reasoning involves using known premises to infer new knowledge in a step-by-step manner, guaranteeing truth through conclusions if all premises are true [33]. For example, given the premises that dogs are mammals and that all mammals have four legs, it can be concluded that dogs have four legs. Inductive reasoning, on the other hand, draws conclusions based on specific observations and may lead to wrong conclusions if observations are incomplete [34], like assuming all swans are white based on distant observations of white swans, which could be incorrect if other swan colours existed. Abductive reasoning involves reaching a plausible conclusion based on observations [35], such as inferring that it rained at night because the grass was found wet in the morning, although other explanations are possible. Analogical reasoning is used to understand one situation by comparing it to another [36]. For instance, someone who knows how to use a computer can use analogical reasoning to understand how to operate a smartphone by drawing parallels between the two. In ML, reasoning refers to the process by which models learn patterns and relationships from data, which serves as the premises. These models then make inferences based on the learned patterns and generate conclusions, such as predictions or decisions on new data [2, 37]. Reasoning in ML is generally informal and relies on inductive, abductive, and analogical reasoning.

2.2.2 Explanation of Multimodal Reasoning

Traditional reasoning involves deriving conclusions from a single modality. In contrast, multimodal reasoning integrates information from various sources to perform a specific task. This requires multiple inferential steps, each with its

own representation [3]. To understand multimodal reasoning, let's consider three modalities for sentiment analysis: image, text, and audio. The process begins by extracting sentiment-related features. This is done by using operation f_1 to integrate text and audio modalities, which results in an intermediate output denoted as O_1 . O_1 is a new representation that contains emotion-related information derived from the original input of text and audio. Next, the intermediate output O_1 is combined with the image modality using another operation, f_2 , to produce the final output \hat{y} . The entire process can be expressed as follows:

$$O_1 = f_1(M_{text}, M_{audio}) \quad (2.2)$$

$$\hat{y} = f_2(O_1, M_{image}) \quad (2.3)$$

In Equations 2.2 and 2.3, f_1 and f_2 represent the reasoning steps that integrate different modalities. Figure 2.2 illustrates the above-discussed multimodal reasoning processes.

Authors in article [4] mentioned four main challenges in multimodal reasoning: structure modelling, intermediate concepts, inference paradigm, and external knowledge. When carrying out multimodal reasoning, structure modelling, which is the first challenge, is essential as it involves organising fundamental elements and their relationships into a hierarchical framework. This framework is then used to comprehend how simpler concepts combine to form more complex ideas. There are several approaches to structure modelling, including hierarchical structure, temporal structure, interactive structure, and structure discovery. Multimodal reasoning involves the use of intermediate concepts in the reasoning process to represent and process data from multiple sources. This technique simplifies and interprets complex multimodal data, making it more manageable for analysis and decision-making in computational models. There are various approaches to intermediate concepts, including attention maps, discrete symbols, and language as a medium. The third challenge in multimodal reasoning involves understanding complex concepts from multimodal data through logical and causal inference. This leads to the cre-

ation of more advanced and unbiased models by considering various possible outcomes. The last hurdle in multimodal reasoning is external knowledge integration, which involves combining knowledge from different domains to define the composition and structure of multimodal reasoning. This type of knowledge includes multimodal knowledge graphs that connect various concepts across modes, as well as multimodal commonsense reasoning that uses deep real-world knowledge for complex media interpretation.

In summary, multimodal reasoning combines various techniques to analyse and understand complicated datasets. This thesis work is based on informal reasoning, specifically inductive, abductive, and analogical reasoning and addresses related challenges by modelling data structures, creating shared representations, enhancing inference mechanisms, and integrating external knowledge.

Figure 2.2: Typical illustration of multimodal reasoning.

2.2.3 Related Work

Based on the foundational concepts of multimodal reasoning, extensive research has been conducted in this area. In the article [38], authors proposed a method named Dual Attention Networks (DANs) for multimodal reasoning, which combines visual and textual attention mechanisms to create representa-

tions of the relationship between vision and language. The article [39] provides a comprehensive overview of natural language reasoning in the context of natural language processing (NLP), offering a clear definition based on philosophical and practical considerations. An article [3] addresses the lack of comprehensive evaluation of diverse approaches for multimodal scientific questions and explanations. In the article, the authors propose the COCO Multi-Modal Reasoning (COCO-MMR) dataset to enhance human-like multimodal reasoning. Many articles explore the ability of multimodal reasoning in large language models (LLMs). For example, in the article [30], authors surveyed existing evaluation protocols of multimodal reasoning for developing LLMs, and in the article [40], authors provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of knowledge on reasoning in LLMs. The authors of the article [5] proposed the multimodal reasoning with multimodal knowledge graph (MR-MKG) method, leveraging multimodal knowledge graphs (MMKGs) to enhance the reasoning capabilities of LLMs.

Numerous articles are available that explore the challenges of reasoning. Articles, including [41, 42, 43, 44, 45], highlight the use of structure modelling approaches that use graph-based neural networks (NNs) to capture hierarchical relationships. These approaches have been applied in various fields, such as visual question answering, machine translation, recommendation systems, web image search, and social media analysis. Intermediate concepts mainly focus on studying how individual multimodal concepts are parameterised in the reasoning process. Several articles have been published that discuss the parameterisation of these concepts. For instance, articles [46, 47] have designed an attention mechanism for parameterisation and reasoning in image captioning generation and visual question answering. In addition, articles [48, 49, 50] use discrete symbols as intermediate steps in multimodal reasoning for tasks such as visual question answering and referring expression recognition. The inference paradigm in multimodal reasoning is concerned with how abstract concepts are inferred from individual multimodal evidence. Articles such as [51, 52] have used logic-based inference techniques to represent knowledge in NNs. Causal inference, on the other hand, extends reasoning from the associational level to

interventional and counterfactual levels. For instance, in article [53], the authors introduce the CLEVRER benchmark that focuses on specific reasoning elements in videos. In addition to CLEVRER, recent works like [54, 55] have proposed Causal VQA and Counterfactual VQA to measure the robustness of VQA models. External knowledge means using large-scale databases to study structure, concepts, and inference. Among the different types of knowledge used, knowledge graphs are widely used to ground structured information, and they offer benefits in visual question answering [56, 57], knowledge base completion [58], and image captioning [59, 60]. Another type of external knowledge reasoning is multimodal commonsense, which requires a deeper understanding of real-world knowledge. Articles like [61, 62, 63, 64, 65] use this type of reasoning, potentially spanning logical, causal, and temporal relationships between concepts, to gain a better understanding of the world around us.

This thesis work distinguishes itself by explicitly focusing on applying informal reasoning to tackle reasoning challenges, mainly when working with unlabelled data and integrating information from different domains. Furthermore, it addresses uncertainty and validates predictions through probabilistic methods, ensuring reliability and robustness in the reasoning that others may not thoroughly examine.

2.3 Multimodal Alignment

2.3.1 What is Alignment?

In general, alignment stands for arranging and creating a structured relationship between different items or entities so they are properly synced. It has different meanings depending on the domain. In ML, alignment implies the process of finding relationships between various sources of data or representation [66].

2.3.2 Explanation of Multimodal Alignment

Alignment is one of the core technical challenges of MML. It helps to identify cross-modal connections and interactions between elements of multiple modalities [4]. Finding the areas of an image corresponding to the captions [67] and syncing the script with the movie [68] are typical examples of alignment. To understand alignment, let's consider the synchronisation of scripts with movies using two modalities: text (script) and visual (movie). Let $T(t)$ and $V(t)$ represent the script and movie, respectively, at the same time t . The objective of alignment is to minimise the difference between the extracted features of the script and the movie over time. To achieve this, two mapping functions $g_T : T(t) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and $g_V : V(t) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ are defined. Here, g_T and g_V map the script and movie content to a feature space \mathbb{R}^d . During the alignment process, the aim is to minimise the integral of the squared Euclidean distance between the features extracted from both modalities over time, which can be expressed as:

$$Align(T, V) = \min_{g_T, g_V} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \|g_T(T(t)) - g_V(V(t))\|^2 dt \quad (2.4)$$

In the Equation 2.4, $\|\cdot\|$ represents the Euclidean distance in the feature space, and the integral from time t_0 to t_1 ensures that the alignment is performed across the full duration of the movie. The output of the alignment provides information on both modalities in a synchronised format, which will help to create new representations that can also be used for classification tasks. Figure 2.3 shows the idea of alignment, where elements of text and visual modality are aligned and generate a new representation or output.

In exploring types of alignment in MML, the discussion in articles [4, 8] provide comprehensive insights. Authors of article [8] categorised multimodal alignment into two types, where at the forefront is explicit alignment, which is further subdivided into unsupervised and (weakly) supervised approaches. The unsupervised variant delves into aligning modalities without direct labels, which is ideal for scenarios where labelled data is scarce or does not exist. In

Figure 2.3: Typical figure of multimodal alignment.

contrast, the (weakly) supervised approach leverages available labels, although sometimes limited, to guide the alignment, making it essential for more structured and specific correspondence tasks. Implicit alignment, while more subtle, plays a similarly crucial role. It operates behind the scenes, forming latent connections that are essential for complex tasks like image retrieval, according to the text description [69]. This type of alignment is further divided into approaches based on earlier graphical models and modern neural network (NN) methods. Graphical models offer a structured approach to alignment that is pivotal in the earlier stages of the field. In contrast, NN-based methods bring adaptability and sophistication, learning to align modalities in a nuanced and data-driven manner.

Additionally, challenges of multimodal alignment have been categorised into three sub-challenges: discrete, continuous, and contextualised representations in article [4]. Discrete alignment is focused on aligning data points from different modalities at specific points or intervals, such as aligning specific words to objects [70]. There are two types of discrete alignment: local and global. Local alignment discovers connections between confined segments of the modality, while global alignment aligns elements across all modalities. Continuous alignment is a method to align continuous signals in cases where segmentation is not easily available. There are two main methods: continuous

warping and modality segmentation. Continuous warping aligns modality elements by forming a bridge in continuous representation space. On the other hand, modality segmentation involves dividing elements into segments based on changes or events. Contextualised representation is a modelling technique that aims to improve representation by accounting for the connections and interactions across different modalities. This technique is classified into three categories: joint undirected alignment, cross-modal directed alignment, and alignment with graph networks [4]. In joint undirected alignment, the goal is to find undirected connections between pairs of modalities where the connections are mostly symmetric in both directions. Cross-modal directed alignment aims to align the source modality in a directed manner with the target modality for asymmetric connections. Lastly, graphical alignment generalises sequential patterns in directed or undirected alignment to arbitrary graph structures between elements.

2.3.3 Related Work

The concept of alignment in multimodal reasoning has been extensively studied in the past few years. However, apart from articles, such as [8, 4], there are not many works that discuss the foundation and classification of alignment and its types. The authors in the article [8] categorised alignment into explicit and implicit. In explicit alignment, subcomponents of instances from multiple modalities are compared. Various works, such as machine translation, text-to-speech, video, and genome sequences, have used supervised and unsupervised approaches to align, as shown in articles [71, 72, 73, 74]. On the other hand, implicit alignment is used as an intermediate step, such as graphical and NNs, to improve the performance of tasks like speech recognition, machine translation, media description, and visual question-answering, shown in articles [75, 76, 77]. According to the updated article [4] on MML, alignment is categorised into discrete alignment, continuous alignment, and contextualised representations. Discrete alignment is significant in identifying connections between discrete elements across different modalities. This is par-

ticularly relevant for tasks where clear segmentation into discrete units. For instance, local alignment techniques have been effectively used in visual co-reference resolution as demonstrated by [78], and in cross-modal retrieval as explored by [79, 80]. These studies underscore the utility of contrastive learning approaches, where representations of the same concept expressed in different modalities are matched, as highlighted in [8]. Continuous alignment tackles the challenges presented by continuous modality signals with ambiguous segmentation. Here, methods based on warping and segmentation play a crucial role. Notably, [81] employs adversarial training to align images with medical reports, representing a novel application of these techniques in a healthcare context. Similarly, [82] introduces both self-supervised and adversarial alignment objectives for multimodal action recognition, showcasing the versatility of alignment methods. The sub-challenge of contextualised representations focuses on capturing the interactions between elements across modalities to improve multimodal representations. Works in this area, such as [83, 84], have used transformer models to capture these undirected connections across pairs of modalities effectively. These models excel in aligning and capturing complementary features at different time steps, demonstrating the growing importance of sophisticated NN architectures in multimodal reasoning.

In this thesis, alignment was conducted in a supervised manner, taking advantage of the simultaneous dataset collection process. The work also tackles challenges such as continuous alignment using synchronised timestamps to manage long-range dependencies and prevent ambiguous segmentation. Establishing a direct one-to-one temporal correspondence simplifies the alignment process while maintaining cross-domain relationships. This straightforward approach allows appropriate mapping without depending on a complex algorithmic alignment process, distinguishing it from existing methods in the literature.

2.4 Multimodal Fusion

2.4.1 What is Fusion?

The term fusion generally refers to the process of merging separate entities into a unified whole. In the ML domain, fusion means integrating data or features from different sources to increase a model's effectiveness for decision-making [8]. Instead of depending on just one source, fusion harnesses the strengths of different sources to yield more reliable results [85].

2.4.2 Concept of Multimodal Fusion

Multimodal fusion is a widely researched topic in MML. It involves combining information from multiple sources or modalities to produce new representations of data to leverage prediction [4, 8]. To comprehend the process of multimodal fusion, let's revisit the examples of aligning text (script) and visual (movie) modalities in section 2.3. After aligning the modalities, the next step involves fusing them to create a useful representation. This fusion can be expressed as:

$$F(t) = h(g_T(T(t)), g_V(V(t))) \quad (2.5)$$

In Equation 2.5, $h(\cdot)$ represents the fusion process that combines the aligned features $g_T(T(t))$ and $g_V(V(t))$ at the same time t . The output of this fusion generates meaningful new representations of both modalities, which can be used for classification tasks. Figure 2.4 shows the fusion of two modalities to generate a new representation of data. This has various benefits, including making more robust decisions by observing the same phenomenon, capturing complementary information not visible in individual modalities, and being able to operate even when one of the modalities is missing. Fusion is used in many applications, such as audio-video speech recognition [86], multiple event detection [87], and medical image analysis [88]. Authors of article [8] categorised fusion into model agnostic and model-based approaches, based on previous works [89, 86, 90, 91].

Figure 2.4: Typical representation of multimodal fusion.

In the model agnostic approach, fusion is not dependent on any specific ML methods and can be split into early, late, and hybrid fusion. Early fusion integrates features without further processing, late fusion integrates after making decisions from each modality, and hybrid fusion combines output from early fusion with individual unimodal predictors. One advantage of this approach is that it can be implemented using any unimodal classifier or regressor. In the model-based approach, data from different modalities are directly combined within the ML models. This is categorised into kernel-based methods, graphical methods, and NNs. In kernel-based methods, the kernel function maps data from different modalities into high-dimensional space for effective integration and analysis. In graphical models, modalities and their interactions are presented using graphical structures. Finally, in NNs-based fusion, models like deep learning are used on large amounts of data from multiple modalities to interpret multimodal data.

To summarise, fusion is a cornerstone in the evolution of ML technologies. Each type of fusion brings unique strengths to the process, making it effective in enhancing the interpretability and functionality of multimodal systems.

2.4.3 Related Work

Multimodal fusion is a significant challenge in the field of MML. There are several survey articles, such as [9, 85, 92], that classify different approaches for fusion with different modalities. Other articles, like [93, 94, 89], provide an overview of fusion methods, with challenges and prospects. Additionally, there are surveys related to the use of fusion in various fields, including healthcare [95, 96], activity recognition [97, 98], and biometric systems [99, 100]. Multimodal fusion approaches have been used to solve many multimodal-related problems in several articles, with the latest being [28], which identified 212 articles where fusion approaches were used to solve MML-related problems across different application domains.

In this research, fusion was performed using two methods: a statistical approach to combine data and the merging of true labels with unlabelled data. The statistical approach provides a quantitative method for integrating information, while the label merging approach enhances supervised learning tasks. These methods address data fusion by balancing statistical accuracy with data enhancement through labelling.

2.5 Transfer Learning

2.5.1 What is Transfer Learning?

Transfer learning (TL) is a category within ML where knowledge gained from solving one problem (the source task) is applied to improve the performance of a different but related problem (the target task) [101, 102]. The primary advantage of TL is that it eliminates the need to train a model from scratch; instead, a pre-trained model can be used to accelerate the training process. This approach is particularly valuable in domains where data availability is limited or computational resources are constrained.

2.5.2 Explanation of Transfer Learning

In recent years, TL has gained significant attention from research communities. While most ML algorithms focus on predicting future outcomes, TL takes a different approach. It connects data from a source domain to a target task in order to find a solution, potentially even a better one. The notation and definitions used here for TL align with the article [101]. Formally, let \mathcal{D}_S represent the source domain and \mathcal{T}_S represent the source task, while \mathcal{D}_T denotes the target domain and \mathcal{T}_T the target task. The main goal is to improve the predictive function f_T for the target task \mathcal{T}_T by leveraging knowledge from the source domain \mathcal{D}_S and the source task \mathcal{T}_S . The concept of the predictive function f_T can be briefly presented as,

$$f_T = \mathbf{T}(f_S, \mathcal{D}_T) \quad (2.6)$$

In Equation 2.6, f_T is the predictive function developed by transferring knowledge from the source predictive function f_S and using data from the target domain \mathcal{D}_T . The operator \mathbf{T} encapsulates the knowledge transfer process, which may involve techniques like fine-tuning pre-trained models, feature extraction, or sharing parameters between models. In Figure 2.5, the process of TL is depicted where knowledge transfers from source to target.

Figure 2.5: Typical representation of transfer learning.

TL revolves around three main questions: what, how, and when to trans-

fer [101, 103, 104]. "What to transfer" refers to identifying which part of knowledge can be transferred across different domains or tasks, while "how to transfer" focuses on determining the methods used for this transfer. Finally, "when to transfer" addresses the specific situations in which TL needs to be applied. TL can be classified into three main types: inductive, transductive, and unsupervised [101, 103, 104]. Inductive TL occurs when the target task is distinct from the source task, regardless of whether the domains are the same or different. The aim is to derive a predictive function for the target task by leveraging knowledge from the source task, often through fine-tuning a pre-trained model. In transductive TL, the source and target tasks are identical, but the domains differ. The objective is to enhance performance on the target domain by transferring knowledge across varying domains, commonly using techniques like domain adaptation to align feature distributions. Finally, unsupervised TL involves both source and target tasks, which are unsupervised learning tasks within different domains.

2.5.3 Related Work

A great way to learn about TL is through surveys, which clearly illustrate its various methodologies and applications. The surveys mentioned in [101, 103] present details of TL, including the algorithms used and the different datasets applied, such as ImageNet for image classification and Amazon Reviews for sentiment analysis. Numerous studies using TL are available across various domains. For instance, in a work of the medical domain, the authors of article [105] demonstrated the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for analysing medical images, where images are related to thoracic CT scans and collected from the LIDC-IDRI dataset. Another article of the same domain [106] explored TL in medical imaging and compared the effectiveness of training CNNs with fine-tuning pre-trained models using the NIH Chest X-ray dataset and the LIDC-IDRI dataset. In work on the vehicular domain, article [107] explored the application of knowledge transfer techniques within federated learning for vehicular ad-hoc networks (VANETs). Their work addressed

specific challenges and proposed potential solutions. Additionally, [108] provided insights into the use of TL for intelligent fault diagnosis in railway systems. They customised algorithms to meet the specific requirements. In the field of NLP authors of article [109] introduced a Universal Language Model Fine-tuning (ULMFiT) approach to perform text classification. In the article [110], the authors introduced the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT). This groundbreaking model is pre-trained on a huge corpus and fine-tuned to perform a variety of NLP tasks. In computer vision, the authors in [111] examined the idea of learning from billions of online images, showing that TL from extensive datasets like ImageNet can be effectively used for different types of visual recognition tasks. Another important contribution was presented in the article [112], where the authors examined how transferable features in DNN could be used in different domains. They conducted experiments using datasets such as CIFAR-10 and ImageNet.

In summary, this study involves sequentially training a model using three labelled datasets from a similar domain. The goal is to transfer knowledge from each dataset to the next to improve outcomes of learning. While the tasks and domains are identical, this method follows the principles of inductive TL, where knowledge from prior training improves performance on later tasks. Furthermore, it also indicates sequential and homogeneous TL, as the transfer of knowledge occurs within the same domain and task in a step-by-step manner.

2.6 Unlabelled Data

2.6.1 What is unlabelled Data?

Unlabelled data refers to datasets that contain raw information but lack corresponding target labels or annotations. This means that the data, for example, a collection of images, does not have any information about the content of each image. The primary distinction between labelled and unlabelled datasets is the presence or absence of labels. In a labelled dataset, each sample is paired with a meaningful label that signifies its class or category, such as in a spam de-

tection dataset, where each email is designated as spam or not. In contrast, in unlabelled datasets, samples exist without these labels, making it challenging to utilise them for decision-making processes.

2.6.2 Approaches for Leveraging Unlabelled Data

In ML, the use of unlabelled data has gained significant attention because of its potential to improve the performance of models without the necessity for extensive manual labelling efforts [113]. It is readily available and not expensive to collect, but total usage is still a challenge [114]. Various techniques can be employed to harness the potential of unlabelled data. One such method is semi-supervised learning, which involves training models by combining a small amount of labelled data with a larger pool of unlabelled data [115]. Unsupervised learning, on the other hand, focuses on identifying patterns and structures in data without the use of labels [116]. It can be achieved through common techniques such as clustering and dimensionality reduction [117]. Additionally, self-supervised learning leverages the inherent structure of data to generate pseudo-labels, transforming unlabelled data into a labelled dataset for training purposes [118].

2.6.3 Related Work

Various approaches are available to handle the challenges posed by unlabelled data. In the article [117], the authors employed a co-training strategy, a semi-supervised approach, to improve classification using unlabelled data. Authors of article [119] addressed the challenges of applying deep generative model (DGM)-based semi-supervised learning algorithms to unlabelled datasets and proposed solutions by combining clustering and semi-supervised learning using DGMs. A novel method was introduced in article [120], which combines a semi-supervised approach with stacking learning (SSC-SL) to enhance soil classification using unlabelled data. Authors of article [121] presented a framework called UnMixMatch, based on semi-supervised learning, to effectively represent unlabelled data and improve performance. A new explainer training

pipeline using Positive-Unlabelled (PU) Learning techniques was proposed in article [122] to train image-based explainers with refined subsets of reliable negative examples. In article [123], authors explored the use of k-means clustering for classifying unlabelled MRI datasets. In a recent article [124], a novel clustering approach was proposed, which allows the pseudo-labelling of a video dataset without human annotations by leveraging the natural correspondence between audio and visual modalities. Additionally, an approach combined with heuristic measures and exhaustive search was proposed to handle both labelled and unlabelled datasets in another article [125].

By effectively using unlabelled data, it is possible to overcome the limitations of relying solely on labelled data and unlock new possibilities in machine learning.

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

This chapter presents an overview of the research methodology and methods used in this thesis. By explaining each step, this section offers a clear understanding of the essential tools and processes employed in the study.

3.1 Research Methodology

Research methodology serves as a structured framework that steers the systematic exploration aimed at resolving research problems. It combines selecting suitable methods and techniques to achieve research objectives efficiently. In this instance, the research was undertaken using exploratory research [126] to design, develop, and validate the proposed solution. Following this phase, applied research [127] was executed to develop and implement solutions, emphasising leveraging algorithms to address identified issues effectively. The research was performed on six levels, and Figure 3.1 displayed the process and how the activities tied together. Each of the levels is discussed further separately.

Figure 3.1: Research methodology with levels.

3.1.1 Problem Identification

The initial phase of the research process involves problem identification, which entails carefully pinpointing the central issue that requires attention. Following the acquisition of relevant data, a comprehensive analysis was conducted to find any hidden obstacles that may impede the achievement of research goals. The analysis highlighted a significant issue within the data, which needs to be addressed before progressing. In summary, the objective of problem identification is to get an in-depth understanding of the data and its limitations and lay a solid foundation for the entire research endeavour by clearly outlining the primary concern that the research seeks to resolve.

3.1.2 Literature review

Identifying and examining the primary themes and gaps in the literature is crucial for sharpening the focus of research. In this phase, an extensive literature review was conducted to identify and analyse existing research and methodologies related to the problem at hand. This review involved exploring previous studies, theoretical frameworks, and methodological approaches to draw meaningful insights that would tell the current research and its gaps. The insights gained from the literature review provide a solid foundation for understanding

the context of the problem and help in developing potential solutions that are grounded in a thorough understanding of the existing body of knowledge.

3.1.3 Problem Formulation

The research problem was carefully formulated based on the identified problem and the knowledge gathered from the literature review. This process involved crafting a clear and concise research question or hypothesis that directly addresses the fundamental challenges. The problem formulation serves as a roadmap for the research, outlining specific objectives and questions that must be tackled. It also provides a clear direction for the study and ensures that all subsequent activities are closely aligned with the overall goal.

3.1.4 Proposed Solution

In response to the specific problem that was identified, a solution was proposed based on a thorough review of existing literature and an in-depth analysis of the data characteristics. The proposed solution requires the development of innovative methodologies or algorithms tailored to tackle the identified issue effectively. This approach aims to harness existing knowledge while incorporating novel strategies where needed. This phase involves comprehensive planning of how the solution would be implemented practically, encompassing the careful selection of suitable tools, techniques, and frameworks. The dataset provided is of utmost importance in the development of the proposed solution. The approach taken in this research is shaped by the unique nature and structure of the data. Therefore, specific techniques and methods are customised to align with its distinct characteristics.

3.1.4.1 Data Acquisition

This subsection provides insight into the origin and characteristics of the data, which was sourced externally rather than being collected. The data was

obtained from Project FitDrive¹ (Monitoring devices for overall FITness of DRIVERs). The experiment took place in Italy and Spain, and vehicular and physiological data were collected during the study. The experiment included capturing vehicular telemetry data and neurophysiological data simultaneously.

Vehicular telemetry data was extensively gathered from vehicles in two distinct environments. The simulator study employed an advanced driving simulator setup featuring a realistic car seat, an authentic dashboard with a steering wheel and manual gear shift, and a display consisting of three monitors, providing a panoramic 160° field of view. As for the real-time study, data was collected from two vehicles, a van and a truck, and both vehicles were equipped with BridgeBox systems to capture vehicular data.

In total, thirty-four professional drivers, all having normal or corrected-to-normal vision, took part in the experiments. These experiments adhered to the ethical standards set forth in the Declaration of Helsinki of 1975, as updated in 2008. In order to minimise the effects of mental fatigue, the experiments were conducted in the afternoon. Prior to the start of the experiments, each participant underwent a thorough 15-minute training session to familiarise themselves with the track and rules. Subsequently, they were tasked with driving a vehicle in both a simulator and real-time for a continuous 45-minute period, in accordance with established scientific protocols [128, 129].

While performing the experiment, two distinct driving routes were used for simulator and real-time study. The real-time driving routes were precisely duplicated in the simulator environment to ensure consistency. The initial group of 17 participants navigated through Route 1 while the remaining participants traversed Route 2. This pattern remained constant for both the simulator and real-time study. In the real-time trials, Route 1 was designated for driving the van, while Route 2 was used for the truck. A steady driving speed of 40km/h was maintained throughout the experiment.

¹<https://www.fitdrive.eu/>

3.1.5 Implementation

The implementation section of a research methodology outlines the actual steps and approaches taken to conduct the research. It provides details about the setup, execution, and adjustments made during the study. In this particular research, the focus was on the practical application of techniques to facilitate multimodal reasoning. The approach involved experimenting with various ML and deep learning (DL) models, testing different scenarios, and thoroughly documenting the outcomes to enhance the effectiveness of multimodal reasoning.

3.1.6 Evaluation

The evaluation section of a research study is a crucial part of the process as it carefully examines the effectiveness of the applied methodologies. In this section, the outcomes of the ML and DL algorithms are carefully scrutinised against predefined criteria and research objectives. It involves analysing the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of the algorithms in the context of the study, often using quantitative measures such as precision, recall, and F1-score. Additionally, this section discusses the significance of the findings, any limitations encountered, and the implications for the field, providing a comprehensive understanding of the impact and applicability of the research.

3.2 Methods

This section summarises the models used in different experimental studies. The papers included in this thesis present details of their implementation. Used methods are categorised by their specific purposes.

3.2.1 Feature Extraction

This sub-section describes the feature extraction methods applied to identify and represent patterns in the data. These methods transform raw data into features and build the foundation for efficient analysis.

3.2.1.1 Multivariate Multiscale Entropy

The Multivariate Multiscale Entropy (MMSE) is a statistical method used to analyse the complexity and variability of multivariate time-series data across different scales [130]. It involves assessing multivariate sample entropy (MsampEn) at various time scales for analysis [131]. Unlike the univariate multiscale entropy (MSE) proposed by Costa et al. [132] for measuring the complexity of a single channel, MMSE assesses the complexity of multichannel observations. The MMSE process involves defining temporal scales through coarse-graining in the first step and calculating MSampEn for each coarse-grained scale in the next step. More detailed information on the calculation and algorithm of MMSE is available in [131, 132, 131, 133].

3.2.1.2 Autoencoder

Autoencoder is a type of artificial neural network (ANN) initially introduced in [134], specifically designed to reconstruct its input. Different variants of autoencoder are available, and they are used in various fields such as computer vision, speech recognition and natural language processing [135]. Usually, autoencoder is popularly used for dimension reduction or feature extraction [136]. The primary aim of the autoencoder is to create a meaningful representation of the data, which can be used for various purposes such as clustering [137, 138]. The autoencoder consists of three components: the encoder, the latent feature space, and the decoder. The encoder and decoder are simple functions with dense layers, and essential information is presented from the original input in the latent feature space. More information on autoencoder is available in articles [135, 137, 138, 139]

3.2.2 Data Segmentation

This sub-section describes the method used for data segmentation. It is essential because it provides a structured view of the dataset, allowing for deeper insights into the data.

3.2.2.1 k-Means Clustering

k-means clustering is an unsupervised algorithm which splits a dataset into non-overlapping subgroups or clusters [140, 141]. The number of clusters depends on the value of a hyperparameter k . During the process, samples are randomly assigned to one of the k clusters. Then, the centroid of each cluster is calculated, and each sample is assigned again to the cluster with the closest centroid. This process repeats until the cluster assignment of each sample stabilises. It is popular because of its efficiency in decision-making. However, apart from benefits, it also has limitations, such as problems in considering an optimal number of clusters and difficulties in the initial position of centroids. More about it can be found in [140, 142].

3.2.3 Classification

This sub-section provides a brief overview of models used in classification tasks. The hyperparameters for each model were explicitly set in the individual experimental studies.

3.2.3.1 Random Forest

Random Forest (RF) is a powerful ensemble learning method has been proposed by L. Breiman in 2001 [143] that is widely used in both classification and regression tasks. In RF, output from multiple decision trees (DTs) is combined to make predictions. During classification tasks, it selects the mode of the predicted classes, while for regression tasks, it averages the individual trees' predictions [143, 144]. One of the key advantages of RF is its ability to mitigate overfitting issues, which is often encountered with single decision trees, as it aggregates multiple DTs to enhance accuracy. Additionally, it offers insights into feature importance, proving invaluable for discerning the most influential factors within the dataset. More insights regarding RF are available in [145, 146].

3.2.3.2 Support Vector Machine

Support vector machine (SVM) was introduced by Vapnik in 1991 [147]. Its main aim is to identify a hyperplane which perfectly separates each class in the feature space. The dimension of the space depends on the input features. It is famous for handling both linear and non-linear classification tasks. Kernel functions are used to handle the non-linearity of the data, and they are called kernel tricks. More additional information on SVM is available in article [148].

3.2.3.3 k-Nearest Neighbors

k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) is a supervised ML method that was first introduced in 1951 by Evelyn Fix and Joseph Hodges [149] and later improved by Thomas Cover [150]. It is a non-parametric method and can be used for both classification and regression tasks. It is popular due to its capability to work with numerical and categorical data. The choice of distance metric and the specific value chosen for k can greatly affect the performance of k-NN. More about k-NN and its techniques can be found in [151, 152].

3.2.3.4 XGBoost

The extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) method is a tree-based learning method that combines the predictions of several models to make a good prediction [153]. It is capable of handling large datasets and can be used for both classification and regression tasks. Moreover, its capability of handling missing values in data makes it widely adopted in many fields. Additional information on XGBoost can be found in the following articles [154, 155].

3.2.3.5 Artificial Neural Network

An ANN is a computational network inspired by the structure of the human brain [156]. Similar to the human brain, each layer of ANN is interconnected with each other. It consists of three types of layers and they are the input layer, the output layer and the hidden layers [157]. In the input layer, data is used

as input. These inputs then pass through multiple hidden layers, where they are weighted, summed up with bias, and go through the activation function. Finally, the output layer provides an output by using the outputs from hidden layers through another activation function. Different kinds of activation functions are available, such as rectified linear unit (ReLU), sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent (tanh), and softmax function. A fully connected multiple-layer neural network is known as multilayer perception (MLP), and it is famous for solving complex classification and regression tasks. More information on ANN is available in [158, 159, 160].

3.2.3.6 Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional neural network (CNN) is a famous DL-based algorithm that is efficiently used in computer vision and pattern recognition tasks in various domains [161]. It has the capability to combine feature extraction and classification into a single learning body. CNN consists of multiple layers, including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, where the convolutional layer is the critical component which mainly extracts features from images like edges and shapes. CNN is a multi-layered feed-forward neural network, enabling it to capture hidden patterns in image [162]. Various CNN architecture are available, such as LeNet [163], AlexNet [164], ResNet [165], and VGG [166], where LeNet is the first CNN architecture specifically designed for recognising handwritten words, which developed by Yann LeCun and his colleagues. For further information on CNN, additional articles are available [161, 167, 168].

3.2.3.7 Transformer

The transformer model has achieved significant success in various ML tasks. It is a DL-based architecture introduced by researchers at Google in 2017 [169]. Since then, several models have been developed based on it. The transformer is a multi-layered architecture created by stacking transformer blocks on top of each other. Each block consists of a multi-head self-attention mechanism, a

position-wise feed-forward network, layer normalisation, and residual connectors [169, 170]. Typically, the vanilla transformer architecture is used to build models, and in some cases, models are constructed by leveraging an encoder or decoder module. The performance of the transformer model depends on the specific task and architecture used. Till now, different transformer models have been introduced for specific tasks, such as vision transformer (Vit) [171], Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [172], Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) [173], Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer (T5) [174] and TabTransformer [175]. More information on the transformer can be found in the references [169, 170, 176, 177].

3.2.4 Validation Approach

This section describes the methods used to validate the result's reliability. These approaches provide a strong framework for assessing the outcome's confidence and consistency.

3.2.4.1 Conformal Learning

Conformal learning is a statistical method used to assess the uncertainty of a model's output by providing prediction intervals and offering reliable confidence [178]. This approach uses the concept of conformity to evaluate how well new examples align with historical data. It is especially advantageous when high reliability is essential, as it allows models to generate valid intervals under minimal distributional assumptions [179]. Conformal learning can be applied to various ML models to enhance the interpretability and robustness of their predictions [180, 181].

3.2.4.2 Bayesian Probability

Bayesian probability is a method that updates beliefs depending on new evidence [182]. It defines probability as a measure of certainty amid uncertainty. It uses prior distributions to represent initial beliefs and then adjusts these through

likelihood functions to determine posterior distributions [183]. This approach is useful in fields where prior knowledge is important, as it enables the integration of domain expertise into the model. By providing probabilistic assessments that account for uncertainty, it improves decision-making and prediction accuracy. More details of Bayesian probability are available in the following articles [182, 184, 185].

Chapter 4

Multimodal Reasoning for Handling Unlabelled Data

This research aims to advance multimodal reasoning to manage unlabelled data effectively. It is important because making decisions using such data is complex. In order to address the challenge, a scheme was developed with multiple inferential steps, and depicted in Figure 4.1. Each step takes input from the previous step and gradually transforms the raw unlabelled data to reach a conclusion. In the scheme, feature extraction and data clustering represent unsupervised learning, while labelling unlabelled data and employing TL represent supervised learning. The output from the extraction, clustering, alignment, and fusion operations is considered intermediate conclusions. In contrast, the results of labelling the data and the final classification are regarded as the final conclusion. All the methods used are referred to as inferences.

The scheme begins with performing feature extraction, where important features are extracted from raw unlabelled data. In the next step, features are clustered into groups. After that, clustered features are aligned with another modality to ensure consistency. In the next step, aligned features are fused to get a unified representation. The reasoning process continues by labelling unlabelled data and making one of the primary conclusions of the scheme. Fi-

nally, the TL approach is applied to labelled datasets to transfer knowledge and make the final conclusion through classification. Therefore, the scheme advances multimodal reasoning by combining various inferential steps. Each step addresses specific challenges of multimodal data and enhances the overall reasoning process. Even in complex scenarios, it allows for more reliable conclusions when working with unlabelled multimodal data.

Figure 4.1: Scheme of multimodal reasoning.

4.1 Feature Extraction

In this research, the dataset containing vehicular information was used, but it had a multicollinearity problem. One way to handle this is feature extrac-

tion [186], which means transforming raw data into a small set of meaningful feature vectors. However, manual feature extraction is complex and time-consuming because it needs domain knowledge, such as deep knowledge of vehicular signals, and careful handling of complexities in data like missing values, outliers, and dimensionality. To handle this challenge, the autoencoder is applied. It is used as an unsupervised feature extraction method. Details of the architecture of the autoencoder are elaborately described in *section 9.3.2.3* of *Paper C*. The performance of the designed autoencoder was evaluated by analysing the reconstruction errors of training and validation datasets during the training of the model and checking the correlation matrix of the encoded features. The loss trend of the training and validation dataset and correlation matrix of extracted features from *section 9.3.2.3* of *Paper C* is presented in Figure 4.2. From Figure 4.2a, the loss indicates a gradual decrease over each epoch, showing consistent improvement and the model is effectively converged at epoch 46. Figure 4.2b presents the correlation matrix of the extracted features where it is observed that there's no strong correlation between features. The model with the same setting as *Paper C* is used in *Paper D*, and the performance is validated in the same way.

In addition to the autoencoder, a statistical approach called MMSE [131] is used to extract features. It also addresses issues related to multicollinearity by focusing on the entropy of the data rather than linear relationships between variables. Detail information about the implementation of MMSE is available in *section 8.3.2.4* of *Paper B*. The entropy values obtained from the MMSE are averaged to check the uniqueness of the representations. In *Paper B*, samples of five groups are used in the MMSE, and the entropy values received for each group are averaged to check for significant differences across groups. Figure 4.3 shows the average entropy of five groups of three classes. From Figure 4.3, it is clear that MMSE effectively distinguishes signal groups by capturing the unique patterns and characteristics of each group.

Figure 4.2: Results after applying an autoencoder and k-means clustering. Figure (a) shows the training and validation loss, and figure (b) illustrates the correlation of features [187].

Figure 4.3: Figure of averaging MMSE of five groups [130].

4.2 Clustering

Performing any classification or regression task on an unlabelled dataset is difficult. Even if features are extracted from unlabelled datasets, they will not make sense. One popular way to find meaning in an unlabelled dataset is to use clustering. Since the used dataset is unlabelled, features extracted using an autoencoder will not make any sense. The k-means clustering algorithm was used to address this. Extracted features from the vehicular dataset were used in the k-means clustering method to group similar data points by minimising the distance to cluster centroids. The value of k for clustering is determined using the elbow method. Detailed information on the k-means clustering with hyperparameters can be found in *section 9.3.2.4 of Paper C*. The output of the clustering algorithm is evaluated by plotting clusters using the t-SNE technique. If it is evident from the plot that all clusters do not overlap, then it can be said that k-means has performed well and properly identified distinct patterns in the data. Figure 4.4 illustrates the results of applying the k-means algorithm on unlabelled data from *Paper C*. The figure shows that all three clusters are separated from each other with minimal overlap. The same k-means algorithm with the settings from *Paper C* is used in *Paper D*, and the performance is validated in the same way.

Figure 4.4: Result of using k-means clustering [187].

4.3 Data Alignment

Alignment is finding relationships between instances of two or more modalities. It helps create a unified representation of modalities. Proper synchronisation and managing the complexities of modalities are the main challenges of alignment. A detailed literature review was conducted on MML and its challenges, including alignment. Various articles are explored in the literature review to understand the definition, application, and challenges of performing alignment in different contexts. *Paper A* is the literature review, and in *section 7.5.5*, details of alignment are discussed. In this research, the unlabelled vehicular dataset was used, which was inefficient because it did not have labels, even though it was extracted and clustered. However, clustering in groups provides meaning that there are patterns in the dataset, but which groups mean what is unknown. To address this issue, supervised alignment is performed where data is aligned with true labels of another modality [188]. So, the extracted unlabelled clustered vehicular dataset was aligned with true labels of neurophysiological data. The alignment process is described in *section 9.3.3.1* in *Paper C*, and the same procedure is followed for alignment in *Paper D*.

4.4 Data Fusion

Fusion is the process of merging data from different modalities. Fused data receive a new representation, which is leveraged to improve performance. However, this process faces several challenges, which involve data heterogeneity, scales, proper alignment, etc. The literature review also included an exploration of fusion. Various articles are examined to understand multimodal data fusion, its types, techniques, and complexities. Details about fusion and its different aspects are details discussed in *section 7.5.6* of *Paper A*.

Different ways are available to perform fusion. In this research, fusion is performed after aligning the unlabelled extracted vehicular data with labels of neurophysiological data. This fusion takes place by simply combining the extracted vehicular feature with the true label. This fusion operation can be called

annotation fusion because the label annotates unlabelled data. This fusion is described in *section 9.3.3.1 of Paper C*. Another type of fusion is performed using MMSE [131]. In MMSE, a single set of entropy values is created by grouping the data into different scales and calculating how often similar patterns appear across all signals. The fusion takes place during the entropy calculation, integrating information from all signals. This type of fusion can be referred to as feature-level fusion, as it involves analysing multiple signals together to create new features. The process of MMSE is outlined in *section 8.3.2.4 of Paper B*.

4.5 Labelling Unlabelled Data

Handling unlabelled data and preparing it for learning includes techniques such as manual annotation, semi-supervised learning, transfer learning, and active learning. In this research, after aligning and fusing extracted unlabelled data with the true labels, the process successfully solved the problem for a few samples. However, a large number of samples were labelled as undefined and need to be labelled. To tackle this, a semi-supervised approach was used [188], where a few labelled samples were used to label the undefined samples. Two ML algorithms were applied for this purpose: RF and XGBoost. The results of the labelled samples using RF and XGBoost are presented in Table 4.1. Subsequently, the same trained models were used to obtain probabilities for the undefined samples. By using the probability scores, the undefined samples were labelled and then merged with previously labelled samples to make a new dataset. After that, the new dataset was applied to RF and XGboost algorithms to evaluate the performance. The results are presented in Table 4.1. From the table, it can be concluded that after labelling the undefined dataset and combining it with the previously labelled samples, it achieves better accuracy than the previously labelled samples. More details about the process are presented in *section 9.3.3.3 of Paper C*, and the results in Table 4.1 have been collected and reorganised from *Paper C*. The same procedure is followed in *Paper D*. Two approaches are used to validate the correctness of labelling using RF and XGBoost. In the first approach, confidence is determined using the probabil-

ity distribution of unlabelled samples on classes, and in the second approach, confidence is determined using Bayesian probability [189]. Details about both approaches with pseudo code are presented in *section 9.3.4 of Paper C*, and the same approach is used in *Paper D* for validation.

Table 4.1: Classification result using RF and XGBoost [187].

Results of Pre-defined Samples			
Method	Train Acc.	Test Acc.	F_1 Score
RF	0.99	0.98	0.98
XGBoost	0.99	0.97	0.97
Results of Aggregated Samples			
Method	Train Acc.	Test Acc.	F_1 Score
RF	0.99	0.99	0.99
XGBoost	0.99	0.99	0.99

4.6 Knowledge Transfer

TL is a ML technique that applies knowledge from a source task to enhance learning in a related target task [101, 103]. Using this approach, a pre-trained model, which is usually trained on a large amount of data, is used to train on a target dataset to get faster convergence and good performance. Several types of TL techniques are available, such as inductive, transductive, and unsupervised TL. In this research, three datasets named C1, C2.1 and C2.2 from the same domain were used, but the number of features was not the same. More about each dataset is presented in *section 10.3.1.1 of Paper D*. The goal is to make a model that contains the knowledge of all three datasets and can provide a good prediction of when unknown samples of the same domain will be provided. So, to meet the goal, an inductive TL approach was applied. The approach related to homogenous and sequential TL, and more about them is described in *Paper D*. A transformer model was developed for TL, inspired by TabTransformer [175]. Details about the developed transfer model were broadly described in

10.3.2.1 of *Paper D*. The figure of the architecture is presented in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Architecture of the transformer model (*Paper D*).

To validate the performance of the developed transformer model, the training and validation loss were carefully evaluated, and conformal learning was used to verify the accuracy of the test results [190]. Before starting the training process, a test set referred to as the Final Test Set was created, consisting of samples from three datasets with an even distribution. Initially, the transformer model was trained on the first dataset, resulting in a saved model known as Model 1. This model was subsequently trained on the second dataset, produc-

ing Model 2. Finally, Model 2 was trained on the third dataset, resulting in Model 3. After the training phase, each model was validated using the initial test set through conformal learning while also being tested against the Final Test Set. The results obtained using the three datasets with the transformer model are presented in Table 4.2. The experiments were conducted in two ways: first, by following the sequential order of the datasets and then by interchanging the order of the last two datasets. The data in the table indicates that, except for Model 3, the conformal accuracy remains above 90%. Additionally, the accuracy for the Final Test Set improves gradually because the models acquire knowledge from each dataset through TL.

Table 4.2: Results of validating trained transformer models using conformal learning (*Paper D*).

Transfer learning in sequential order				
Models	Dataset	Train Acc.	Conformal Acc.	Acc. on Final Test Set
Model 1	C1.	0.98	0.93	0.54
Model 2	C2.1	0.91	0.88	0.79
Model 3	C2.2	0.90	0.82	0.80
Transfer learning changing sequential order				
Models	Dataset	Train Acc.	Conformal Acc.	Acc. on Final Test Set
Model 1	C1.	0.98	0.93	0.54
Model 2	C2.2	0.97	0.91	0.80
Model 3	C2.1	0.90	0.87	0.82

The developed transformer model was also applied individually to each dataset, and the results were compared with traditional ML algorithms: SVM, k-NN, and RF. In Table 4.3, the results indicate that, except for ANN, the others did not achieve enough accuracy.

Table 4.3: Summary of the classification of transformer and traditional machine learning methods (*Paper D*).

Model	Evaluation Matric	C1	C2.1	C2.2
Transformer Model	Test Acc.	0.98	0.90	0.93
	F_1	0.98	0.90	0.93
SVM	Test Acc.	0.80	0.81	0.88
	F_1	0.80	0.81	0.88
k-NN	Test Acc.	0.82	0.81	0.87
	F_1	0.82	0.81	0.87
XGBoost	Test Acc.	0.98	0.79	0.80
	F_1	0.98	0.79	0.80
ANN	Test Acc.	0.94	0.89	0.90
	F_1	0.94	0.89	0.90

Chapter 5

Summary of the Included Papers

5.1 Paper A

Title: A Systematic Literature Review on Multimodal Machine Learning: Applications, Challenges, Gaps and Future Directions.

Authors: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shahina Begum.

Abstract: Multimodal machine learning (MML) is a tempting multidisciplinary research area where heterogeneous data from multiple modalities and machine learning (ML) are combined to solve critical problems. Usually, research works use data from a single modality, such as images, audio, text, and signals. However, real-world issues have become critical now, and handling them using multiple modalities of data instead of a single modality can significantly impact finding solutions. ML algorithms play an essential role in tuning parameters in developing MML models. This paper reviews recent advancements in the challenges of MML, namely: representation, translation, alignment, fusion and co-learning, and presents the gaps and challenges. A system-

atic literature review (SLR) was applied to define the progress and trends on those challenges in the MML domain. In total, 1032 articles were examined in this review to extract features like source, domain, application, modality, etc. This research article will help researchers understand the constant state of MML and navigate the selection of future research directions.

Status: Published in IEEE Access (Volume:11). Publisher: IEEE.

Authors' Contribution: Arnab Barua is the main author of the paper. He developed research questions to carry out the review and collected scientific articles. Upon discussion with Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, the criteria for the selection of articles were established. Furthermore, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed and Shahina Begum contributed with their valuable ideas, writing, discussions, and reviews.

5.2 Paper B

Title: Multi-scale Data Fusion and Machine Learning for Vehicle Manoeuvre Classification.

Authors: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shahina Begum.

Abstract: Vehicle manoeuvre analysis is vital for road safety as it helps understand driver behaviour, traffic flow, and road conditions. However, classifying data from in-vehicle acquisition systems or simulators for manoeuvre recognition is complex, requiring data fusion and machine learning (ML) algorithms. This paper proposes a hybrid approach that combines multivariate multiscale entropy (MMSE) and one-dimensional convolutional neural networks (1D-CNNs). MMSE is utilised for early feature extraction and data fusion, and the extracted features are classified using 1D-CNNs, achieving an impressive 87% test accuracy in multiclass classification. This paper provides insights into

improving vehicle manoeuvre classification using advanced ML techniques and data fusion methods to handle complex data sets effectively. Ultimately, this approach can enhance the understanding of driver behaviour, inform policy decisions, and develop more effective strategies to enhance road safety.

Status: Published in 2023 IEEE 13th International Conference on System Engineering and Technology (ICSET).

Authors' Contribution: Arnab Barua is the primary author of this paper. Alongside Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, the problem was formulated. Arnab Barua developed the methodology, preprocessed the data, and created the MMSE and 1D-CNN models for fusion and classification. Additionally, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed and Shahina Begum contributed valuable ideas, writing, discussions, and reviews.

5.3 Paper C

Title: Second-Order Learning with Grounding Alignment: A Multimodal Reasoning Approach to Handle Unlabelled Data.

Authors: Arnab Barua, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shaibal Barua, Shahina Begum and Andrea Giorgi.

Abstract: Multimodal machine learning is a critical aspect in the development and advancement of AI systems. However, it encounters significant challenges while working with multimodal data, where one of the major issues is dealing with unlabelled multimodal data, which can hinder effective analysis. To address the challenge, this paper proposes a multimodal reasoning approach adopting second-order learning, incorporating grounding alignment and semi-supervised learning methods. The proposed approach illustrates using unlabelled vehicular telemetry data. During the process, features were extracted

from unlabelled telemetry data using an autoencoder and then clustered and aligned with true labels of neurophysiological data to create labelled and unlabelled datasets. In the semi-supervised approach, the Random Forest (RF) and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithms are applied to the labelled dataset, achieving a test accuracy of over 97%. These algorithms are then used to predict labels for the unlabelled dataset, which is later added to the labelled dataset to retrain the model. With the additional prior labelled data, both algorithms achieved a 99% test accuracy. Confidence in predictions for unlabelled data was validated using counting samples based on the prediction score and Bayesian probability. RF and XGBoost scored 91.26% and 97.87% in counting samples and 98.67% and 99.77% in Bayesian probability, respectively.

Status: Accepted in the 16th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence (ICAART 2024). 2024.

Authors' Contribution: Arnab Barua led the study and is the primary author of this paper. He, along with Shaibal Barua, formulated the problem. Arnab Barua developed the methodology, preprocessed the data, and created methods for aligning and fusing unlabelled vehicular and neurophysiological data. The validity of these methods was confirmed by Mobyen Uddin Ahmed and Shahina Begum. Andrea Giorgi provided valuable input on data collection and processing. Finally, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed, Shaibal Barua, and Shahina Begum made significant contributions through their ideas, writing, discussions, and reviews.

5.4 Paper D

Title: Advanced Hybrid Reasoning and Transfer Learning on Multimodal Data with Transformers.

Authors: Arnab Barua. Mobyen Uddin Ahmed and Shahina Begum.

Abstract: Reasoning is a vital process in machine learning (ML), involving making inferences and drawing conclusions based on data. This capability is important for developing intelligent systems which can understand and predict complex patterns. The study investigates reasoning through two distinct methodologies: multimodal reasoning and transfer learning based reasoning. In the first approach, multimodal reasoning is used with a semi-supervised method to label unlabeled datasets. In the second approach, transfer learning has been used to transfer knowledge of data from one model to another. Both approaches are demonstrated using unlabeled vehicular telemetry data. During processing, three sets of telemetry data are used to extract features separately through the autoencoder. These features are then clustered and aligned to create labelled and unlabeled datasets. The eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm achieved over 98% test accuracy when applied to the labelled datasets and was then used to predict labels for the unlabeled datasets, which were later added to the labelled dataset to form three datasets for further processing. In transfer learning, a transformer model specifically designed to handle continuous features is developed. Labelled datasets are applied to the transformer model, one after the other, resulting in three final models, with each model achieving over 80% accuracy. The model's prediction confidence is also validated using conformal learning, where the final models achieved over 80% accuracy. The transformer model is also separately trained on the datasets and compared with traditional machine learning models, outperforming the others by achieving an accuracy of 98%. By building on the groundwork laid by this study, future research can push the boundaries of what is possible with reasoning approaches, opening up new paths for scientific exploration and practical applications in different fields.

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methodology and attention-based models for multimodal reasoning. Additionally, Mobyen Uddin Ahmed and Shahina Begum provided valuable insights through their ideas, writing, discussions, and reviews.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Limitations

This thesis aims to advance multimodal reasoning for handling unlabelled multimodal data. Throughout the research, various methods were developed and evaluated. The following sections discuss the findings of this research, including the answers to the RQs defined in *section 1.3*, the limitations of the study, and conclusions with future research directions.

6.1 Discussion

Reasoning is an essential aspect in the development of AI systems [191]. The complexity of multimodal data requires reasoning to integrate and interpret effectively [3]. The goal of this research is to advance multimodal reasoning to handle multimodal unlabelled data effectively. The main aim is to use reasoning as an abstract concept and a tool to manage unlabelled data properly. By handling such data, reasoning provides benefits in several aspects, including accurate decision-making, effective real-time analysis and finding insights from the data.

While working with multimodal reasoning, several difficulties arise, such as the absence of labels and the challenge of integrating diverse types of information for proper representation. To tackle those difficulties, a structured

approach to reasoning is necessary. This research uses a scheme with several inferential steps to meet the necessity. The designed scheme consists of six inferential techniques, as mentioned in *Chapter 5*. Several studies are conducted to design each inferential step by analysing its necessity and capability for providing a solution. Feature extraction is the first inferential step, which is necessary for extracting relevant features [186]. This extracted information gets a new representation and is leveraged to provide a good solution. The second inferential step is clustering, which is crucial for finding patterns in unlabelled data by grouping them. Clustered data also helps to identify outliers in the data and provides an overview of data, which can help for further processing [140]. Alignment and fusion are the third and fourth inferential steps. Alignment and fusion are the third and fourth steps of inference, where datasets are aligned based on their relationships and then fused together [66, 85]. After aligning and fusing, a new form of data comes out with a new representation, which supports performing a more refined analysis. Following this, in the next inferential step, unlabelled data is labelled using the semi-supervised approach [188]. The main motivation for this approach is using a low amount of samples for labelling data. By doing this, the models used in this approach make a good contribution. The performance of the used model is validated by using the confidence score of two methods. In the final inferential step, the TL approach [101, 103] is used to transfer knowledge between datasets to leverage a good prediction. An advanced ML-based method was used for this task to get good accuracy in classification.

The designed scheme is demonstrated by the unlabelled vehicular dataset and labelled neurophysiological dataset with the aim of handling the unlabelled vehicular data by integrating neurophysiological data and making conclusions like predicting the driver's mental stage. Used datasets are part of a project and were collected by another team and shared as part of a collaborative effort to address specific challenges related to unlabelled vehicular data. The main reason behind choosing this dataset is that it lacked predefined labels and contained complexity, which allowed for a more practical demonstration of the proposed scheme. In contrast, benchmark datasets are often curated and labelled to stan-

standardise testing conditions [192]. With the designed scheme and the data, this research presents how reasoning can be improved through a series of inferential stages.

As a whole, this thesis produced a scheme for advancing multimodal reasoning in the context of handling unlabelled data by overcoming inherent challenges to provide useful insights. The outcomes of the thesis contribute to multimodal reasoning in MML and offer effective solutions for managing complex, unlabelled datasets across various domains. A summary of the thesis outcomes is provided by addressing the research questions along with corresponding sections and included papers. Furthermore, this section discusses the challenges encountered during the research studies conducted for this thesis, followed by an analysis of the limitations.

6.1.1 Discussion on Research Question 1

How effective are existing data fusion and alignment methods and how to improve them in the context of MML?

Multimodal data frequently varies in structure, scale, and noise, which requires effective methods for integration and synchronization. Data alignment [66] and fusion [85] techniques can help address these challenges, enabling MML systems to process and analyse complex data more efficiently [8]. By examining the strengths and limitations of these techniques, it becomes possible to enhance them and develop new approaches to tackle the unique challenges posed by multimodal datasets.

In this research, RQ1 focuses on exploring existing multimodal alignment and fusion techniques in MML. An extensive literature review was performed to answer this question, and *Paper A* contained this review. From the review, it is clear that managing multiple challenges at the same time can be difficult. Therefore, it is not essential to tackle all challenges in order to solve one problem. Instead, addressing one or two key challenges that align with the main task is sufficient. The literature review detailed various existing approaches to fusion and alignment. After conducting this literature review, it became clear

which techniques are most commonly used, their typical applications, and the challenges they face in real-world scenarios. Additionally, the review finds gaps in current research, suggesting areas where further development is needed to enhance fusion and alignment processes.

The review highlighted that NN-based models, such as autoencoders, are mostly used for alignment. A notable challenge in this area is the need for methods to properly manage unstructured and complex data across different modalities, each with its own data structure. To effectively handle issues of multimodal alignment, it is crucial to focus on identifying relationships between modalities, creating concept-wise modality representations, and overcoming ambiguity present in high-dimensional data. Challenges related to fusion are more extensively addressed in MML research than others. In the past, model-agnostic approaches were commonly employed, but with the advancements in ML, model-based methods such as NN, graphical models, and kernel-based techniques have become more popular for performing fusion. However, a significant issue still exists: effectively merging modalities with different data characteristics and structures. By developing flexible and advanced model-based fusion techniques, researchers can enhance model performance by accommodating diverse types of data.

This review not only answered the RQ by outlining existing techniques but also placed a groundwork for exploring new methods that could improve multimodal reasoning, particularly in handling unlabelled data. To support this RQ, another work is performed in *Paper B* where a fusion is performed using a statistical approach named MMSE. It measures complexity and irregularities in multivariate data across different scales, without model training. It provides clear insights into the structure and interactions of data, whereas ML methods rely on training predictive models to find patterns.

6.1.2 Discussion on Research Question 2

How can multimodal heterogeneous data be effectively used in the absence of labelled data?

Multimodal data is heterogeneous because it contains different types of information from various sources [193]. Integrating the characteristics and structures of each modality into a single model poses challenges. One characteristic of multimodal data is unlabelled data [194], often produced due to the difficulty and cost of manually annotating diverse data on a large scale. In real-world scenarios, data is collected from multiple sources, resulting in vast amounts of unlabelled multimodal data.

Handling multimodal data is important as it contains complex real-world information. Integrating multiple data types is necessary to find hidden patterns. To effectively manage this complexity and predict outcomes in various applications, more accurate and robust models are required. In light of these challenges, the aim of RQ2 is to find a solution for effectively labelling data in the absence of true labels. *Paper C* addresses this question by applying a semi-supervised approach to generate labels for unlabelled datasets. The model's performance improved by using both labelled and unlabelled data. This approach not only helps in processing complex multimodal data but also advances the ability of MML systems to reason with incomplete information.

6.1.3 Discussion on Research Question 3

How advanced ML techniques can enhance the efficiency of multimodal reasoning?

The field of ML consists of advanced methods such as autoencoders, CNNs, recurrent neural networks (RNNs), and others, which are good at handling complex data processing and analysis tasks. In the context of multimodal reasoning, each algorithm plays a crucial role in the inference process, gradually transforming raw multimodal data into valuable insights [3]. Through the implementation of multiple inferential steps, multimodal reasoning effectively handles and integrates diverse data types, thereby enhancing the system's overall comprehension and decision-making capabilities. This strategic approach exponentially boosts the efficiency of multimodal reasoning by ensuring precise

processing and alignment of each data type, ultimately leading to more resilient and dependable outcomes.

The main objective of RQ3 is to explore how advanced ML algorithms can effectively enhance multimodal reasoning. This RQ is answered in *Paper C* and *Paper D*. In each paper, several inferential steps are used to make conclusions. In *paper C*, several inferential steps are used to label unlabelled datasets. These inferential steps include feature extraction and data labelling, as presented in Figure 4.1. *Paper D* is the continuation of work *Paper C* where, in the end, the TL approach is used to transfer knowledge for robust prediction.

6.1.4 Discussion on Research Related Issues

6.1.4.1 Data

The data used in this research was collected by another research team and made available for analysis. The data comes from two domains: vehicular and neurophysiological. In total, six datasets were provided, three related to vehicular and three related to neurophysiological. The vehicular dataset includes one from the simulator and two from real-time vehicle driving. Using pre-collected data offers benefits such as eliminating the need to handle the data collection process and speeding up the research timeline. However, using externally collected data also has challenges, such as a lack of knowledge about the data collection process and potential biases. Overall, there are trade-offs in collecting data first-hand or using pre-collected data, but if the focus is on developing methods for a specific task, the data collection process is not a significant concern.

6.1.4.2 Selection of Feature Extraction Method

Two approaches are used to extract features: one involves using MMSE, and the other involves using autoencoder. The MMSE is a statistical method that calculates entropy values to measure the variability and interactions between multiple signals [130, 131]. This method is described in *section 8.3.2.4* of *Pa-*

per B , and it helps extract entropy-based features that quantify the complexity and variability of multivariate time-series data across different temporal scales [131]. MMSE has several advantages, such as capturing the complexity of individual signals and the interactions between multiple signals, thus providing a comprehensive set of features for analysing multivariate time-series data. However, it also has limitations, including the need for high computational intensity to calculate entropy across multiple scales and the potential sensitivity to parameter choices, which can impact the robustness of the extracted features.

Autoencoder is an unsupervised approach popular for extracting features from unlabelled datasets [186]. In this particular research, an autoencoder is used to extract features from an unlabelled vehicular dataset. Previous research studies have used different types of autoencoder architectures, but in this study, a basic vanilla sparse autoencoder is used [195], employing a sparsity constraint through techniques like regularisation. A summary of this architecture is available in *section 9.3.2.3 of Paper C*, and the same architecture is used in *Paper D*. There are multiple benefits to choosing this type of autoencoder for research, including feature selection, anomaly detection, dimensionality reduction, noise reduction, and producing robust features for better generalisation. However, it also has certain drawbacks, such as limitations in handling complex data, sensitivity to hyperparameters, and the potential for loss of information and overfitting. Despite these limitations, the advantages of this type of autoencoder make it an excellent choice for analysis. In this research, the autoencoder aids in knowledge representation by capturing non-linear relationships. The primary objective is to use it to achieve less correlated features because the features of the used dataset have a high correlation. As shown in Figure 4.2, the features extracted from the autoencoder have less correlation. Since there is no established guideline for determining the number of features the encoder can produce, the experiment is conducted multiple times. This involves adjusting the number of layers and output shapes and tuning hyperparameters, which help to get features with less correlation. After fine-tuning and evaluating the model's performance for each set of hyperparameters, the number of extracted features is fixed at seven, resulting in features that are less correlated.

MMSE and autoencoder take different approaches to feature extraction. MMSE uses a statistical technique to extract entropy-based features that capture linear relationships and offer a straightforward interpretation of the data without using a learning model. On the other hand, an autoencoder is an NN-based model that learns to encode input data into a lower-dimensional latent space and then reconstructs it back to its original form. Autoencoder is powerful for feature extraction because it can capture complex, non-linear relationships in the data and create compact representations. In the context of MML, an autoencoder is generally better because it can learn joint representations that capture the complex relationships between different modalities. MMSE, while helpful in understanding the complexity of multivariate time-series data, is not inherently designed for multimodal data integration. Thus, MMSE is less effective for MML because it has the limitation of handling diverse and heterogeneous data as effectively as an autoencoder.

6.1.5 Reason behind clustering

In this research, the clustering approach is used to find hidden patterns in the unlabelled vehicular dataset. The primary reason for this choice is that even without proper labels, the feature extraction process in unlabelled data effectively functions as a dimensionality reduction problem. So, to mitigate this challenge, the k-means clustering algorithm is used, which splits the dataset based on similar characteristics [140, 141]. It is used instead of others like DBSCAN or hierarchical clustering due to its simplicity, efficiency, and scalability, especially when handling large datasets. It also has limitations, like sensitivity in primary centroid placement and the need for predefined cluster numbers. Despite having limitations, it is often used as a reliable tool in data analysis because of its ability to provide a clear view of the context.

6.1.6 Data alignment and fusion

In this research, supervised alignment [188] is used to match unlabelled vehicular data with the true labels of neurophysiological data. This is done for

two main reasons. First, unlabelled vehicular data on its own doesn't provide any meaningful information, so aligning it with other data creates significance. Second, both the vehicular dataset and the neurophysiological dataset were captured at the same time, so there is a time-based relationship. The significance of this alignment lies in transferring knowledge from neurophysiological data to vehicular data, which improves the learning process.

After performing alignment, data is fused to obtain a new representation and later used for further processing. This research explores two types of fusion. The first approach involves simply combining unlabelled datasets with true labels of another dataset, which can be called annotation fusion. This is a straightforward approach where integration is performed without deeply analysing or transforming the features. The second approach involves fusion using MMSE, which is known as feature-level fusion [8]. This method does not involve ML models and combines multiple signals to create new features. However, it mainly focuses on internal data relationships within a single modality and may not be as effective in multimodal learning, as it does not integrate multiple types of data. In multimodal learning, models are used to represent and learn from multiple data types by capturing cross-modal interactions. Therefore, while MMSE provides valuable insights into a single modality, it may not fully explore the potential of multimodal data and may be less suitable for tasks requiring the integration of multiple sources.

6.1.7 Semi-supervised for data labelling

A semi-supervised learning approach was used to label unlabelled datasets. Semi-supervised is the combination of both supervised and unsupervised learning where a small amount of labelled data is used alongside a larger amount of unlabelled data [188]. After aligning and fusing the dataset, some samples still need to be properly labelled, and this is the reason behind applying a semi-supervised approach. It efficiently handles data, improves performance, and is flexible for any data and tasks. Along with advantages, it also has disadvantages like the risk of incorrect labelling and the need for careful validation of

the model's performance on labelling.

The contribution of semi-supervised learning lies in the positive results it has produced, which can be observed in two ways. First, it validates the trustworthiness of used models in accurately classifying data, and second, it demonstrates the potential of semi-supervised techniques in properly using labelled and unlabelled data. As previously discussed, one challenge of semi-supervised learning involves carefully validating the models. Two approaches were used to address this. The first approach involves using thresholds to determine the accuracy of the models in predicting the class of unlabelled samples. In this approach, probability scores are used as a metric of confidence. The second approach employs Bayesian probability to validate the model's predictions [189]. This is done by comparing the initial prediction probabilities with posterior probabilities.

6.1.7.1 Method for transfer learning

Three unlabelled datasets are labelled using the above-described approach, but a model that leverages the shared knowledge of three datasets to improve performance is necessary. For this reason, in this research, TL was applied, which used the knowledge gained from a pre-trained model, usually trained on a large dataset, to improve the performance of a model on a new task which has less data [101, 103]. A transformer-based model is used for TL. Usually, different kinds of DL-based methods like CNN, RNN, and traditional ML algorithms like SVM and k-NN are used in TL, but they contain several limitations compared to the transformer. For example, CNN is efficient for image data analysis, and RNN mostly struggles with long-term dependencies because of problems like vanishing gradients [174].

Traditional ML methods typically rely on manually engineered features and often struggle to handle large datasets for capturing complex patterns properly, like DL models [196]. These methods have the limitation of hierarchical feature learning capability which is available in NNs, and particularly advantageous for TL. In contrast, transformer models are employed in TL because they can

learn overall feature representations from large datasets. Their self-attention mechanism helps them understand and leverage context more effectively, making them versatile across different domains. Additionally, transformer architecture enables the transfer of pre-trained models to new tasks with minimal fine-tuning, often resulting in improved performance and faster convergence compared to other methods.

To test the accuracy of the model's predictions, conformal learning is used [190]. Unlike traditional validation methods like k-fold cross-validation, leave-one-out cross-validation, and bootstrap, which estimate overall model performance, conformal learning creates prediction intervals that are guaranteed to contain the true outcome with a specified probability. This is especially helpful in situations where understanding and quantifying uncertainty is important. It offers the key advantage of generating prediction sets with guaranteed coverage probabilities, which ensures that the true value falls within these sets with a specified confidence level. However, a notable drawback is the computational intensity, especially for large datasets.

6.2 Limitations

- The feature extraction process used in this research involves representing raw data in a different form while retaining information from the original dataset. The main focus is on minimising the reconstruction loss to ensure that the model effectively learns and encodes features that contain the most relevant aspects of the data. However, minimising the reconstruction loss does not guarantee that the encoded features possess the most pertinent information. Therefore, while the model may be able to reconstruct input accurately, it does not necessarily mean that the learned features are the most meaningful for subsequent tasks such as classification or prediction. This lack of confidence in the information of the encoded features could impact the robustness and reliability of the outcomes.

- In this study, the semi-supervised learning approach for labelling unlabelled datasets heavily relies on the clustering of the data. Clustering algorithms may produce different results on the same dataset based on their sensitivity and randomness in their initialisation. In the context of this research problem, if the clustered data doesn't align correctly with the true labels, there's a risk of incorrect labelling. Therefore, the accuracy of clustering is crucial, as incorrect cluster representation of the data could lead to erroneous decision-making in subsequent tasks.
- The semi-supervised approach involves using a small amount of samples to label a large number of samples. In this research, both RF and XGBoost were used, and the results were validated using Bayesian probability and counting the frequency of samples of each class. However, it's important to note that there is a risk of overfitting when training RF and XGBoost with a small dataset. Models trained on a small dataset can easily memorise specific patterns, including noise, and struggle to generalise, leading to overfitting. Sometimes, the validation process may also fail to capture this issue. Ultimately, overfitting can mislabel the dataset and impact the generalizability of the models.
- In this research, TL makes decisions using extracted features instead of raw data. The main reason for this approach is that, although the data are from the same domain, there is inconsistency in the number of parameters. Additionally, during learning, the implemented model relies on the same input dimensionality. Therefore, the training process was confined to using only the extracted features, which had consistent dimensions across the datasets. While extracted features offer a standard representation, they may not capture all the detailed information contained in the raw data.
- The transformer developed in this research was explicitly designed to handle continuous features. It is adapted from the TabTransformer, which is typically used to handle tabular datasets containing categorical

and constant features. By focusing specifically on continuous features, the model optimises its performance for datasets with this type of data. In this research, the vehicular dataset with continuous features is used. However, it should be noted that if categorical features are introduced in future datasets, the current transformer model may not process these features properly. On the other hand, the TabTransformer architecture could potentially be adapted to incorporate both continuous and categorical data. Nonetheless, there is no certainty that it would perform well with such data types. This limitation indicates that the current model lacks the flexibility to handle diverse data types encountered in real-world applications.

The overall limitations of this research come from several factors which are not severe but can impact the scope and applicability of the findings. These include the use of pre-collected datasets, which may have issues with data quality and variability, potentially leading to biases. Also, the focus on a single domain may limit the generalizability of the model to other domains, requiring further adjustment. Additionally, the use of advanced ML algorithms requires significant computational resources, which may not be available in all practical settings. Furthermore, the research is limited to specific evaluation metrics, indicating the need for further exploration. While these limitations are not severe, they point to opportunities for future work to enhance the generalizability of the systems.

6.3 Conclusion and Future works

The main goal of this thesis is to enhance multimodal reasoning for effectively handling unlabelled data. This is accomplished by creating a scheme consisting of several inferential steps, with each step having a specific task to manage unlabelled datasets. The inferential steps include feature extraction, clustering, alignment, fusion, a semi-supervised approach, and TL. Two conclusions are drawn: the first one uses a semi-supervised approach by labelling an un-

labelled dataset, and the second one involves transferring knowledge between datasets using a transformer-based model. The work is demonstrated using an unlabelled vehicular dataset and labelled neurophysiological data.

Three RQs have been formulated for this study. The first RQ aims to explore the existing alignment and fusion approaches in MML. The second RQ will focus on exploring potential methods for effectively handling unlabelled multimodal data. Lastly, the third RQ will delve into advanced ML algorithms for enhancing multimodal reasoning. By addressing these RQs, this research has made three key contributions. Firstly, it has identified current developments, limitations, and research gaps in alignment and fusion in MML. Secondly, it introduces techniques for labelling unlabelled data for further processing. Finally, by using advanced ML models such as transformers to advance multimodal reasoning, the research has made significant strides. Four research papers have been added, each addressing all RQs and making valuable contributions.

The study also acknowledges its limitations and identifies areas for future research. Building upon the findings, future work will focus on the development of models that not only make predictions but also provide comprehensive explanations for the reasoning behind their decisions. These models will have the ability to move beyond simplistic categories of reasoning, such as formal or informal, to a more nuanced understanding of how decisions are formed.

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